

EM-style Framework for Task-Driven Differentiable Synthesizer Optimization: Rationale, Design, and Backpropagation through Reaction–Diffusion Systems

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Abstract

This technical report presents a diagnostic study on differentiable synthesizer optimization. It consists of two closely related but distinct parts.

Part I examines the rationale for using downstream-task feedback to optimize synthetic data generators. We revisit the motivation originating from Klein et al. [17, 19], analyze its empirical limitations, and discuss supporting evidence from Meta-Sim and Task2Sim. We then introduce an EM-style framework that alternates between trainer and synthesizer optimization.

Part II investigates backpropagation through reaction–diffusion systems, a concrete and challenging instantiation of the differentiable synthesizer that was explored during the development of the EM-style framework. We provide theoretical details of several approaches (truncated BPTT with intermediate supervision, implicit differentiation, adjoint method, and Krylov solver), present an empirical diagnosis of the loss landscape on a Gray-Scott system, and outline renewed solution directions.

Code and experimental materials are available at <https://github.com/Yan-Yang-bot/bp2renderer>.

Keywords: differentiable rendering, reaction-diffusion systems, task-driven synthetic data, EM-style optimization, loss landscape diagnosis

Part I

Task-specific downstream feedback and EM-style framework

1 Revisiting the rationale of training task-specific synthetic data generators

The motivation for the present work originates from Klein et al. [17]. According to Klein, downstream-task feedback — whether manual or automatic — provides an efficient way to optimize the data synthesizer. One of their claims is that such feedback allows the synthesizer to emphasize only the features most useful for the downstream task, offering advantages over simply matching the full real-image distribution.

However, the empirical results claimed in the original paper now have issues: they can no longer prove the advertised advantages [19]. As the demonstrated advantages become less clear, the need for extra effort in using downstream-task feedback (instead of directly comparing against real data) turns unverified.

The present section therefore re-examines whether this need still exists. In other words, we re-examine whether the original reason for that need, i.e., the claimed advantages, can still be confirmed by other means. To this end, we consider Klein’s own strengthening arguments in the PubPeer reply [19] together with two closely related papers that also use downstream-task feedback to inform their data synthesizers.

In the PubPeer reply, Klein strengthens the original claim by noting that while modern generative models excel at cross-domain generation (different styles or perspectives), they often struggle to produce sufficiently

diverse and nuanced variations within a very specific domain — such as disease patterns of a particular plant–disease combination for which no extensive training data is available. They suggest that a task-driven approach similar to their paper could still be highly effective in such ultra-specific, data-scarce scenarios.

Meta-Sim [7] and Task2Sim [12] provide further empirical context for this rationale. Meta-Sim [7] uses a distribution-matching loss (MMD in feature space) as the primary objective and downstream-task performance as an optional meta-objective. Their controlled experiments show that optimizing the distribution-matching loss already leads to substantial improvements in downstream task performance on real validation data, while the additional task feedback provides only marginal further gains. Task2Sim [12] goes further by making downstream accuracy the central signal and demonstrates across 20 diverse tasks (including medical and aerial imagery) that different downstream problems indeed favor markedly different simulation configurations; a one-size-fits-all synthetic dataset is therefore suboptimal, and task-adaptive generation consistently outperforms non-adaptive baselines.

Taken together, research from 2022 demonstrates that task-specific downstream-task feedback already brings measurable advantages even in broad, general-domain scenarios through controlled comparisons, and Klein’s strengthened argument suggests that the advantages may be even greater in ultra-specific, data-scarce regimes requiring highly nuanced intra-domain variations. Our EM-style framework builds directly upon this rationale. While the rapid progress in conditional generative models since 2022 may have reduced the practical necessity of explicit task-driven feedback in many domains, and whether and to what extent this progress has maintained its value in the most extreme data-scarce, ultra-specific niches remains untested by controlled comparisons in the current literature, our ultimate focus on backpropagation through reaction–diffusion systems still contributes to a more foundational technical challenge in differentiable physics-informed simulation, one that remains relevant independently. The coming sections will start from introducing the EM-style algorithm, follow with a focused study on the backpropagation through reaction–diffusion systems (theoretical details, experiments, result discussions, and potential future directions), and end with a list of relevant studies in the literature and potential generalized applications.

2 Problem Definition

Reaction-Diffusion systems serve as a generative physical simulator, and under certain tasks (e.g., texture synthesis or pattern generation), it can be interpreted as a differential generator (denoted $R(\cdot)$ in this paper) from latent rule space to spatial patterns, used to stochastically generate patterns from a set of latent variables \mathbf{z}_R , with \mathbf{z}_R including a subset of unfixed hyperparameters, initial conditions, boundary conditions, etc. These patterns, in turn, can be used as synthetic data x for machine learning training purposes.

$$x = R(\mathbf{z}_R) \tag{1}$$

However, the search for an optimal set of \mathbf{z}_R is often performed manually, which does not provide a good promise of success. Here, we propose a bi-level (EM style) training approach that updates the target training neural network and the reaction-diffusion renderer alternatively to achieve an optimal renderer and a workable trainer simultaneously.

3 Algorithm

Let θ_T denote the parameters of the target trainer network. The squared loss function of a function with parameter θ at a data point x , i.e., an input-label pair (d, t) , is defined as:

$$\text{loss}(x, \theta) = \text{loss}((d, t), \theta) = \|d\theta - t\|^2 \tag{2}$$

For a training data set $\mathbf{x} = \{x_i\}_{i=1}^N$, the MSE loss over the entire training data is defined as

$$\text{loss}(\mathbf{x}, \theta) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \text{loss}(x_i, \theta) \tag{3}$$

3.1 The E-M Style Algorithm

See Algorithm 1. Why is it wrong yet useful? It illustrates the core alternating idea without stability constraints and the long back propagation remedy. “2.2 Issues and Potential Solutions” provides more discussions.

Algorithm 1 E-M Style Algorithm

Require: T : number of iterations, n : batch size,

$R(\cdot)$: stochastic function turning z_R to synthesized data,

z_{R0} : initial value of z_R , θ_{T0} : initial value of θ_T ,

η_T : trainer’s learning rate, η_z : renderer’s learning rate

- 1: Initialize $z_R \leftarrow z_{R0}$, $\theta_T \leftarrow \theta_{T0}$
 - 2: **for** $t = 1$ to T **do**
 - 3: **E-step:** Expectation of the target training model parameters under current renderer
 - 4: Generate a batch of training data $x = \{R(z_R)^{(i)}\}_{i=1}^n$ {Fixed generator z_R , stochastic sampling via $R(\cdot)$ }
 - 5: Update trainer: $\theta_T \leftarrow \theta_T - \eta_T \nabla_{\theta_T} \text{loss}(x, \theta_T)$
 - 6: **M-step:** Maximization of renderer performance under current trainer
 - 7: **for** $i = n + 1$ to $2n$ **do**
 - 8: Update generator: $z_R \leftarrow z_R - \eta_z \nabla_{z_R} \text{loss}(R(z_R)^{(i)}, \theta_T)$
 - 9: **end for**
 - 10: **end for**
 - 11: **return** synthesizer $R(\cdot)$, trainer θ_T
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3.2 Issues and Potential Solutions

3.2.1 How can we ensure training stability?

More specifically, can this approach perform zero-shot learning without collapsing into low-diversity equilibria, where both the trainer and the renderer co-adapt without improving generalization?

Potential solutions: 1. Train the trainer on some real data before doing the alternating training.
 2. Use some regularization strategies (adding an extra regularizing term to the loss) to prevent lazy adaptation.

Two Notions of “Shortcut-Free” Optimization: In our setup, avoiding shortcuts has two distinct meanings:

Classifier-level generalization. A classifier trained on synthetic steady-state patterns must generalize to real data, rather than exploiting artifacts specific to the differentiable simulator.

Representation-level generalization. The pattern generator (e.g., a reaction–diffusion system) should produce representations that remain useful when consumed by other classifiers—i.e., not only the one used during code-based training.

These correspond to two kinds of robustness:

Type-1 generalization (model robustness)

Type-2 generalization (representation robustness / transferability)

3.2.2 The backpropagation to the reaction-diffusion system

Backpropagation through the reaction-diffusion system will involve a long chain of steps, making it very time-consuming and prone to exploding/vanishing gradients.

Potential solutions:

1. Can truncated BPTT or intermediate step supervision (e.g., Loss = (MSE(step=20) + MSE(step=40) + MSE(step=60) + MSE(step=100)) / 4) be useful here?

2. We can also consider forward-forward as an alternative, but the original form of forward-forward pushes each computing step toward what is favored by the final classification, which is no problem for the target classifier, but might very likely flatten the reaction-diffusion evolution trajectory and smooth out the surge, competition, and emergence into just a shortcut.

3. Certain R-D systems can use implicit differentiation. When an R-D system reaches equilibrium, its time-discretized update rule

$$u_{t+1} = u_t + \Delta t F(u_t; \theta),$$

where $u_t \in \mathbb{R}^n$ denotes the system state at time t , θ represents the parameters of the RD dynamics, and $F(\cdot; \theta)$ is the reaction–diffusion operator, can be stated as

$$u^* = u^* + \Delta t F(u^*; \theta),$$

where u^* denotes the equilibrium state. This is equivalent to the steady-state condition

$$F(u^*; \theta) = 0.$$

Thus, if we want to propagate the partial differentiations regarding the data (here, the data is u^*) further to those regarding the data generator parameters θ , we can utilize the nonlinear equation $F(u^*; \theta) = 0$. When we can solve the equation and get $u^* = G(\theta)$, we can easily get the next multiplier in the differentiation chain, $\nabla_{\theta} u^*$. Otherwise, if the PDE contains complex reaction terms (such as Grey-Scott), making a closed-form solution for $\nabla_{\theta} u^*$ impossible, a more sophisticated solution, such as would be needed (but still better than backpropagation through time stepping), may be required.

4 Backpropagation as the Future Focus

Choosing a reaction-diffusion system, as in Section 3.2.2, is not a must for the general topic of EM-Style algorithm. The renderer part in the EM-Style algorithm can be anything simpler but at the same time differentiable. For example:

- Differentiable Rendering
- Soft Rasterizer: if the differentiable renderer contains a soft rasterizer, and we only want to optimize the resulting pixel colors (patterns), there is a closed-form solution for a one-layer-only back propagation step from the classifier’s input images to the parameters of the renderer.

Instead, discussing specifically backpropagating to reaction-diffusion systems extends our paper to the different topic of optimizing (or the inverse of) physics-informed generators.

On the other hand, although controlled comparisons up to 2022 (notably Task2Sim) already demonstrate measurable advantages of task-driven feedback even in broad scenarios, the rapid progress in conditional generative models since then may have altered the practical necessity of explicit downstream-task feedback in many cases. In the ultra-specific, data-scarce regimes that motivated this work, the value of task-driven optimization remains an open and important question that awaits further controlled comparisons with modern conditional diffusion baselines.

Therefore, the EM-style approach developed here is retained at its present stage of development, serving as both a closure to my research initiated under the supervision of Klein et al. [17] and a foundation for future investigation. The technical challenge stemmed from this framework, the unfavorable loss landscape in reaction–diffusion systems, would be the primary focus of Part II, and my continued work, should further supervision or funding become available, may focus on this, too.

5 Brief Literature Review

Related Methods:

- **Meta-Sim**[7], **Task2Sim**[12]: Feedback from task to data simulator, but not fully end-to-end differentiable.
- **Dataset Distillation**[10]: Backpropagation from classifiers to synthetic data, without a true data generator.
- **Generative Teaching Networks (GTN)**[9]: EM-like approach where the generator is a neural network itself; lacks physical-law priors but may use real data initialization.
- **GAN Inversion**[11] + **Optimization**: No physical priors; optimizes input vectors based on discrepancy between generated and real data.
- Many simulator/renderer optimizations employ **REINFORCE**[2] for task-driven updates, whereas differentiable simulators allow direct gradient-based optimization.
- **Alternating Optimization / Coordinate Ascent**[3]: The alternative updates between data generator optimization and model training are similar to Expectation-Maximization (EM), a classic example of alternating optimization or block coordinate ascent. The E-step and M-step optimize over two disjoint variable blocks, but both steps maximize the same objective (the evidence lower bound).

Also, a discussion of Physics-Informed Neural Networks can be found at the end of Section 8.

Part II

Backpropagation through reaction–diffusion systems

This part zooms in to look at issues from one part of the framework: the backpropagation to the reaction-diffusion system.

6 Theoretical Details of Methods

Here we detail the methods proposed in the second part of Section 3.2, i.e., those for the backpropagation problem.

6.1 Intermediate supervision and truncated BPTT.

In a long reaction–diffusion (R–D) rollout $x_0 \rightarrow x_1 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow x_T$, one plausible strategy is to place supervision at selected intermediate states. Concretely, we choose a set of indices $\mathcal{K} = \{k_1, k_2, \dots\}$ —for example based on stability, energy decrease, or simply fixed intervals—and attach losses of the form

$$\mathcal{L} = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \lambda_k \ell(f_\theta(x_k), y),$$

where $\ell(f(x), y)$ is different from the “loss” defined previously, and denotes the loss of the output of classifier f when input data is x and ground truth label is y .

After these losses are defined, optimization is still carried out by *backpropagation*: each term $\ell(f_\theta(x_k), y)$ backpropagates through the classifier and then through the discrete R–D steps

$$x_k \rightarrow x_{k-1} \rightarrow x_{k-2} \rightarrow \dots,$$

supplying gradients to the learnable R–D parameters (treated here as differentiable-renderer parameters) and, where applicable, to the input variables.

This backpropagation may optionally be *truncated*, meaning that for each supervision point x_k , gradients are propagated backward only for a fixed number of steps instead of all the way back to x_0 . In other words, the choice of *supervision locations* happens during the forward pass, whereas *gradient truncation* is a decision about the backward pass. The two ideas are conceptually independent.

6.2 Solving the steady-state for $\frac{dU}{d\theta}$ (implicitly)

Implicit Differentiation[5]. We treat the steady-state pattern $U^*(\theta)$ of the reaction–diffusion system as an implicit function of the parameters θ , defined by

$$F(U^*(\theta), \theta) = 0. \tag{4}$$

Differentiating both sides with respect to θ gives

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial U}(U^*, \theta) \frac{dU^*}{d\theta} + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \theta}(U^*, \theta) = 0. \tag{5}$$

Let $J = \frac{\partial F}{\partial U}(U^*, \theta)$ denote the Jacobian of F with respect to U . Assuming J is nonsingular, the implicit function theorem implies that $U^*(\theta)$ is differentiable and

$$\frac{dU^*}{d\theta} = -J^{-1} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \theta}(U^*, \theta). \tag{6}$$

If a classifier is applied to the steady-state pattern to produce a scalar loss $L = \mathcal{L}(U^*)$, then by the chain rule

$$\frac{dL}{d\theta} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial U^*} \frac{dU^*}{d\theta}. \tag{7}$$

Adjoint Method[6]. Let $U \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^p$. Equation 7 can be written as the linear system

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial U}(U^*, \theta) V = -\frac{\partial F}{\partial \theta}(U^*, \theta), \tag{8}$$

which yields the sensitivity matrix $V = \frac{dU^*}{d\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times p}$. Here the Jacobian $J = \frac{\partial F}{\partial U}(U^*, \theta)$ is an $n \times n$ matrix, and $\frac{\partial F}{\partial \theta}(U^*, \theta) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times p}$. Numerically, this corresponds to solving p linear systems with the same $n \times n$ coefficient matrix and $n \times 1$ right-hand sides (one for each column of V).

We use the adjoint method as a trick to reduce this cost. Expanding Equation 7 gives

$$\frac{dL}{d\theta} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial U^*} \frac{dU^*}{d\theta} = -\frac{\partial L}{\partial U^*} \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial U}(U^*, \theta) \right)^{-1} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \theta}(U^*, \theta). \tag{9}$$

Instead of explicitly forming V , we introduce an adjoint row vector $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times n}$ defined by

$$\lambda \frac{\partial F}{\partial U}(U^*, \theta) = \frac{\partial L}{\partial U}, \quad (10)$$

or, equivalently,

$$\left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial U}(U^*, \theta) \right)^\top \lambda^\top = \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial U} \right)^\top. \quad (11)$$

Thus we only need to solve a *single* linear system with an $n \times n$ coefficient matrix and an $n \times 1$ right-hand side to obtain λ^\top , instead of p such systems for the columns of V . The gradient with respect to θ is then recovered as

$$\frac{dL}{d\theta} = -\lambda \frac{\partial F}{\partial \theta}(U^*, \theta). \quad (12)$$

Krylov method[1]. Solving either for v or λ may use numerical methods. Here we use the Krylov method. We set an initial value for λ as λ_0 and calculate λJ iteratively. Following each calculation, we update λ using the residual $\frac{\partial L}{\partial U^*} - \lambda J$ with a learning rate α .

The calculation of $\lambda J = \lambda \frac{\partial F}{\partial U}(U^*, \theta) = \frac{\partial}{\partial U}(\lambda F(U^*, \theta))$ can be implemented as follow with $X = U^*$:

Algorithm 2 Row-vector-Jacobian product: computing λJ without forming J .

Require: $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times n}$, $X \in \mathbb{R}^n$, parameters θ .

- 1: Define the scalar function

$$\phi(X) = \lambda F(X, \theta).$$

- 2: Compute its gradient with respect to X :

$$\lambda J = \nabla_X \phi(X) = \frac{\partial}{\partial X}(\lambda F(X, \theta)).$$

- 3: **return** λJ .
-

7 Empirical Results

Based on the above analyses, we designed and conducted experiments on backpropagation-based optimization of a Gray-Scott system. The design and result details are provided in the Appendix “Diagnosis Report for Gradient-Based Optimization of a Dynamical System.”

Experimental Observation: The system was tasked with fitting four parameters (Du , Dv , F , k) against a batch of 512 target patterns of size 128×128 , generated at known ground-truth values ($Du=0.16$, $Dv=0.08$, $F=0.035$, $k=0.065$). Despite a robust experimental setup—enforcing numerical stability via adaptive learning rate, restricting parameter ranges through reparameterization, and satisfying the CFL stability criterion—loss values fluctuated within a narrow band throughout training with no convergence trend, even when parameter updates were reduced to an extent that hundreds of iterations were required for any minimally meaningful displacement in parameter space. The appendix includes further probes showing cross-sections of the loss landscape along each parameter axis, together with corresponding multi-contrast animations at multiple points on these axes.

Interpretation: The loss landscape cross-sections (Fig. 2 in the Appendix) reveal sharp cliffs along each parameter axis, likely corresponding to bifurcations between uniform steady-state regions and pattern-forming regions. The high-loss side of each cliff corresponds to all-0 or all-1 solutions, which provide no meaningful gradient signal. The optimizer was mostly navigating this region, with only very occasional brief excursions into the pattern-forming side—which explains the near-uniform loss plateau observed during

training. Critically, the gradient-based approach inherits this landscape regardless of how gradients are computed: whether via backpropagation through unrolled steps, implicit differentiation, or a surrogate network trained on the same parameter-to-steady-state mapping, the parameters-loss mapping remains identical. Alternatives along these lines therefore do not resolve the issue.

The loss landscape cross-sections also show that, on the pattern-forming side of the cliffs, steady-state patterns change gradually and regularly (though extremely slowly) as parameters vary along the axes investigated, suggesting that this region is in principle traversable. There is also an indication that such regular change is even more prominent at intermediate time steps prior to convergence to steady state—and notably, at those earlier steps, gradual variation across parameters may be present on both sides of the cliff, including in trajectories that ultimately converge to uniform solutions. To what extent this can be exploited remains to be explored.

8 Renewed Solution Based on Empirical Results

The diagnosis above points to three possible directions for a viable backpropagation through reaction-diffusion systems:

(a) Better loss function design. A loss function that provides meaningful gradient signal within the pattern-forming region—making it reliably traversable once reached—combined with a mechanism to avoid or escape the uniform steady-state region. The observed regularity of steady-state patterns across parameter variation within the pattern-forming region suggests that a well-designed loss there is possible.

(b) Intermediate supervision. Incorporating supervision at intermediate time steps, rather than only at steady state, may provide gradient signals that the current terminal-state loss cannot. How intermediate patterns should contribute to the total loss requires careful design to avoid conflating transient behavior with the target regime. If this can be used efficiently, even the uniform steady-state regions may be traversed via gradients.

(c) Time-conditioned surrogate model. A surrogate neural network trained to map $(Du, Dv, F, k, t) \rightarrow \text{pattern}$, with simulation time step t as an extra input dimension, may allow the optimizer to search over earlier time steps where the parameter subspace has more tractable loss geometry, and subsequently transfer progress to a better final-state prediction. This is viable when the goal is to generate target-like patterns for downstream use rather than to find an exact mapping between steady-states and parameters.

***PINN as a candidate of (c).** A possible candidate of the surrogate model in (c) is a Physics Informed Neural Network (PINN) [8, 16]. In PINN’s first definition, where the PDE parameters are fixed, its network mapping $(x, y, t) \rightarrow (u_{x,y}, v_{x,y})$ [8, 16] is equivalent to $t \rightarrow (U, V)$, where U and V represent full images at time step (t) . This equivalence is because, at any time step, all index pairs (x, y) have corresponding pixel values. Subsequently, PINN development made PDE parameters trainable in the residual loss, facilitating inverse problems [8, 16]. This redefines the mapping as $(Du, Dv, F, k, t) \rightarrow (U, V)$, which is equivalent to my surrogate model concept in (c).

While PINN presents advantages of needing less data points in its existing inverse problem applications in the literature, whether this advantage still holds on Gray-Scott’s structure with complex bifurcations needs to be investigated. Successful performance of PINNs typically occurs in scenarios with mild loss landscapes [15, 4], whereas the limited PINN application to the Gray Scott model [14] addressed forward problems only, without trying to solve inverse problems. How PINN performs on inverse problems when there are bifurcation structures in general is discussed in [18], but it can only fit bifurcation at a single attractor without the capability of global accuracy fitting. This background indicates that we should exercise caution when determining whether a naive feedforward network or a complex PINN is the better surrogate.

Alternatively, we can use a PINN to learn the Gray-Scott parameters from a given target pattern. However, it is much more costly each time compared with amortizing computation by performing a one-time surrogate training and using lightweight learning whenever a target is provided, and it may not be able to be chained with a downstream application and trained in an end-to-end fashion.

***Surrogate the reaction terms only.** In [13], the authors proposed a backpropagation-compatible reaction–diffusion model in which the reaction term is parameterized by a neural network without being constrained by any predefined physical law. Replacing the reaction term in this manner renders the loss landscape more amenable to optimization via backpropagation. However, this surrogate is not tied to any specific reaction–diffusion family (such as the Gray–Scott model) and does not impose consistency with known physical laws. Consequently, the learned equation, while formally a PDE, may not correspond to a physically interpretable reaction mechanism. A natural direction, therefore, is to design a surrogate that remains backpropagation-compatible while explicitly preserving correspondence with the Gray–Scott family.

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